

Bone fragility in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Influence of sex and cardiovascular disease in a pilot study using metabolomics

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ABSTRACT

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is one of the most common worldwide metabolic disorders, characterized by insulin resistance (IR) and defective insulin secretion by pancreatic β -cells which leads to multiple complications such as bone fragility. This complication might be influenced by other factors such as gender and cardiovascular disease (CVD). However, it is unclear why a certain T2DM group develops bone fragility, and what the molecular mechanism is. Metabolomics is a powerful approach to the study of human metabolism, especially in complex diseases such as T2DM. Thus, this study aimed to identify significant metabolites associated with bone fragility in T2DM patients. To achieve this, 81 individuals were enrolled and classified as T2DM patients (D, n=28), T2DM with bone fragility (D-Frag, n=25), or age-matched non-diabetic subjects (ND, n=28) as the control group. Serum samples were collected and analyzed using liquid chromatography and gas chromatography, both coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively). Samples were compared within four different scenarios: 1) the classical comparison of **D vs ND** to corroborate previous studies; 2) **D-Frag vs D** to explore the metabolites mainly associated with bone fragility; 3) the same comparison using male data (**MD-Frag vs MD**) to study as a more homogeneous model of bone fragility as in women, bone fragility could be mainly associated with

Abbreviations: AGEs, Advanced Glycation End Products; AP, Abdominal perimeter; BCAA, Branched-Chain Amino Acid; BMD, Bone Mineral Density; BMI, Body Mass Index; BRFE, Batch Recursive Feature Extraction; CID, Collision-Induced Dissociation; CV, coefficient of variation; D, diabetic group; D-Frag, Diabetic group with bone fragility; DG, Diacylglyceride; EI, Electron Impact; ESI, Electrospray Ionization; GC, Gas Chromatography; GC-MS, Gas Chromatography coupled to Mass Spectrometry; IGFR, Insulin-like growth factor; IR, Insulin Resistance; LC, Liquid Chromatography; LC-MS, Liquid Chromatography coupled to Mass Spectrometry; LPC, Lysoglycerophosphatidylcholine; LPE, Lysoglycerophosphatidylethanolamine; m/z , mass charge relation; MPP, Mass Profiler Professional; MS/MS, Tandem mass spectrometry; MS, Mass spectrometry; MSCs, Mesenchymal Stem Cells; ND, Non-diabetic group; NIST, National Institute of Standards and Technology; NMR, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy; PC, Glycerophosphatidylcholine; PCA, Principal Component Analysis; PE, Glycerophosphatidylethanolamine; PLS-DA, Partial-Least-Square Discriminant Analysis; PPAR γ , Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor gamma; QC, Quality Control sample; Q-TOF, Quadrupole Time-Of-Flight; RT, Retention Time; SM, Sphingomyelin; T2DM, Type 2 Diabetes mellitus; TG, Triglyceride; TUS, Total Useful Signal; UHPLC, Ultra-High Performance Liquid Chromatography; UV, univariate.

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hormonal stage and pregnancy; and 4) **MD-Frag-CVD vs MD-CVD** to explore the influence of bone fragility in the male-based model with CVD considering that most of the T2DM patients suffer from CVD. After analysis of these scenarios, our results suggest that acylcarnitines and glycerophospholipids, among other metabolites, are involved in the development of bone fragility in T2DM.

Introduction

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is one of the most common worldwide metabolic disorders with a massively increasing prevalence [1]. Over the past decades, the T2DM population has increased by more than doubled, especially in developed countries as a consequence of genetic and epigenetic determinants, but significantly due to environmental risk factors such as sedentary behavior, dietary factors, and smoking, among others [2–4]. It is estimated that by 2030, T2DM prevalence will increase by 54% to reach the number of 439 million people with this disease [5] and this number is expected to rise to 783 million by 2045 [6].

T2DM is a complex multifactorial disease characterized by insulin resistance (IR) and defective insulin secretion by pancreatic β -cells [7–9]. T2DM is closely linked to several complications mainly macro and microvascular complications and bone disorders. In particular, bone fragility is a complication with a high socio-economic impact in the T2DM population. In this context, osteoporotic fractures currently constitute a significant public health issue, and this risk is even greater in T2DM patients concretely on hips, wrists, and feet [10]. Hence, multiple studies have suggested that the skeleton has additional functions beyond its structural role as an insulin-target tissue, thus, playing a highly important role in glucose and energy homeostasis and metabolism [11–14].

The duration of T2DM affects bone health in the advanced stages of the disease, where complications such as hyperglycemia, the formation of toxic Advanced Glycosylated End-products (AGEs), and chronic inflammation severely affect the structure and architecture of the bone [15–18]. Several studies have analyzed bone mineral density (BMD) in relation to fracture risk. Although no correlation has been found between mineral content measured by DXA and diabetic bone fragility, the scientific evidence points to impairment of bone microarchitecture as the cause of bone fragility in the diabetic population [15,17,19,20]. Firstly, hyperglycemia dysregulates the fine balance of adipogenesis and osteoblastogenesis through stimulation of mesenchymal stem cell (MSC) differentiation into adipocytes and, by down-regulating the Wnt/protein kinase C osteoblast differentiation pathway [16,18,20,21] which negatively affects bone quality by increasing adipogenesis, bone marrow fat, and bone loss. Likewise, AGEs formation alters the normal cross-linking between collagen fibers resulting in brittle bone with impaired biomechanical properties [12,22]. In addition, metabolic stress, caused by hyperglycemic conditions, stimulates osteoclast proliferation and suppresses osteoblastogenesis, leading to increased bone resorption and bone loss [18,19]. All these T2DM complications ultimately deteriorate the skeleton and affect the biomechanical properties of the bone tissue increasing its propensity to fracture. Thus, the results derived from complex techniques such as high-resolution peripheral quantitative computed tomography (HR-pQCT) [23] as well as those derived from other non-invasive imaging techniques such as Trabecular Bone Score (TBS) [24], have evidenced the low bone quality and higher cortical porosity in patients with T2DM. However, there is no evidence as to why certain T2DM patients develop bone fragility while others do not.

Additionally, in women, bone fragility has been associated with the hormonal stage (menopause) and pregnancy [25–27]. However, to our knowledge, no study has been conducted solely on men with T2DM. Thus, a study on men with T2DM would provide a more homogeneous model to better understand the molecular mechanisms in bone fragility.

Similarly, cardiovascular disease (CVD) represents another major complication in many T2DM patients [28]. Previous studies have

demonstrated that the oxidative stress induced by the accumulation of AGEs inhibits MSCs proliferation, induces MSCs apoptosis, and prevents the differentiation of these stem cells into bone, cartilage, or adipose tissue [29]. Therefore, the progenitor cell alteration induced by T2DM leads to poor vascularization during tissue repair, hence, patients suffer from vascular deficiencies that suggest a pre-state of CVD [12,18]. However, the intimate relationship between T2DM and CVD has not been revealed. For these reasons, it is critical to identify biomarkers for a clearer diagnosis of bone fragility in T2DM patients. To achieve this objective, metabolomics provides a powerful tool for the study of human metabolism allowing a better understanding of the pathogenesis of these complex diseases [30–34]. This is especially useful through the untargeted analysis approach, where after analyzing the differences in the metabolic profiles of the groups, significant metabolites, and biological pathways can be characterized [30,33]. Therefore, the aim of this study was to analyze the metabolic differences between T2DM patients with and without bone fragility, and the influence of sex and CVD on this pathology.

Materials and methods

Clinical study and patient characteristics

The study recruited a group of patients with T2DM ($n=53$) diagnosed according to the criteria of the American Diabetes Association (2005) from January 2006 to March 2007 [35]. Patients were enrolled as soon as they attended the clinic for treatment. For the non-diabetic group (control group, $n=28$), age-matched subjects were recruited from the general population during the same period.

Inclusion criteria were Caucasian, age between 35 and 65 years, normal values for hemogram, renal creatinine, liver function, calcium, and phosphorus. Exclusion criteria were chronic pathologies other than T2DM affecting bone, and previous or current treatment with drugs affecting bone metabolism.

All patients underwent body mass density (BMD) measurement on the lumbar spine, femoral neck, and hip bones. T2DM patients were sub-classified as "non-fragile bone, defined as D" or "fragile bone, defined as D-Frag" based on the results obtained according to the criteria established by the World Health Organization [36], and as "CVD" or "not CVD" according to the presence of prevalent CVD. Inclusion criteria for CVD were cerebrovascular disease (ischemic stroke or transient ischemic attack), coronary heart disease (previous myocardial infarction, diagnosed unstable angina, coronary revascularization surgery, or percutaneous coronary interventions), or ischemic peripheral arterial disease.

The study was approved by the ethics review board of the San Cecilio Hospital in Granada, Spain (Project ID: PI 0514±2012. Research Ethics Committee of Granada Center (CEI-Granada) on 26 November 2012) and conformed to the principles of the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki All study participants gave written informed consent.

Metabolomic fingerprint

To increase the metabolite coverage a multiplatform analysis was carried out using liquid and gas chromatography both coupled to high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively) following previous studies [37–40]. Specifically, for LC-MS, the experiments were performed on a UHPLC system (1290 Infinity LC system,

Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany), consisting of two degasers, two binary pumps, and a thermostated autosampler, maintained at 4 °C. The LC system was coupled with 6550 iFunnel QTOF MS detector, in positive electrospray ionization (ESI) mode. Complementary, for GC-MS, samples were measured on a GC system (Agilent Technologies 7890A) consisted of an autosampler (Agilent Technologies 7693) and an accurate-mass analyzer Q-TOF (Agilent Technologies 7200). Sensitivity of both instruments is shown somewhere else [41,42].

Liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry with a quadrupole-time of flight mass analyzer (LC-ESI(+)-QTOF-MS)

Sample treatment. Serum deproteinization and metabolite extraction were performed by mixing 100 µL of the sample with 300 µL of cold (−20 °C) methanol/ethanol mixture (1:1, v/v). Samples were vortex-mixed, kept on ice for 5 min, and centrifuged at 16,000 × g for 20 min at 4 °C (centrifuge 5415 R Eppendorf). The resulting supernatant was collected into LC vials [43].

Instrumental analysis. In brief, 0.5 µL of each sample was injected into a reverse-phase column (Poroshell 120 EC-C8 150 × 2.1 mm, 2.7 µm; Agilent Technologies) thermostated at 60 °C. The gradient used for the analysis consisted of a mobile phase A (10 mM ammonium formate in Milli-Q water) and mobile phase B (10 mM ammonium formate in MeOH/IPA (85:15, v/v) pumped at 0.5 mL·min^{−1} flow rate. The chromatography gradient started at 75% phase B, increasing to 96% B in 23 min, and was maintained for 8 min until 31 min. The gradient then was increased to 100% B until 32.5 min and returned to starting conditions by 33 min, followed by 7 min of re-equilibration time, taking the total run time of 40 min. Data were recorded in full scan mode from 100 to 1200 *m/z* with a scan rate of 1.02 scans·s^{−1}. The capillary voltage was set to 3500 V, the drying gas flow rate was 11 L·min^{−1} at 290 °C, gas nebulizer 40 psi, fragmentor voltage 175 V, and octopole radio frequency voltage (OCT RF Vpp) was 750 V. Two reference masses were used all over the course of the analysis: *m/z* 121.0509 (protonated purine) and *m/z* 922.0098 (protonated HP-921) for constant mass correction. Samples were randomly prepared and analyzed throughout the run.

Data treatment. The raw data obtained by the LC-MS was cleaned of background noise and unrelated ions by the Batch Recursive Feature Extraction (RFE) tool included in MassHunter Profinder software B.08 (Agilent). The RFE algorithm creates a list of masses and RT, associated with the abundance of the possible components representing the full TOF masses from the spectral data. Each component is the sum of co-eluting ions that are related by charge-state envelope, isotopic distribution and/or the presence of different adducts and dimers. In order to find co-eluting adducts of the same feature, the following adducts were selected: [M+H]⁺, [M+Na]⁺ and [M+NH₄]⁺ for LC-MS data.

Metabolite annotation. The significant entities from LC-MS were first annotated at MS1 level using the online platform CEU mass mediator [44]. Secondly, to increase the confidence of the annotation, targeted MS/MS analysis was performed on significant entities with the same chromatographic conditions used for the primary analysis. Ions were targeted by collision-induced dissociation (CID) fragmentation at 20 eV based on the previously determined accurate masses and RT [45–47]. If available, experimental MS/MS spectra were compared with those reference spectra contained in the public database (Human Metabolome Data Base; HMDB).

Gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry with a quadrupole-time of flight mass analyzer (GC-QTOF-MS)

Sample treatment. Serum samples were deproteinized by mixing 40 µL of plasma with 120 µL of cold acetonitrile (−20 °C) following a previously described methodology [48]. Samples were then vortex-mixed for 2 min, let stand on ice for 5 min, and centrifuged at 16,000 × g for 10 min at 4 °C. From the resulting supernatant, a volume of 100 µL was

evaporated to dryness using a Speedvac Concentrator (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, MA). Methoxylation was performed with 20 µL of *O*-methoxyamine hydrochloride (15 mg·mL^{−1}) in pyridine. For silylation, 20 µL of BSTFA with 1% TMCS was added to each vial and placed at 70 °C for 1 h. Finally, 100 µL of 10 ppm C18:0 methyl stearate in heptane was added as an internal standard to each vial and all samples were vortex-mixed for 2 min before being placed in the GC-MS [48].

Instrumental analysis. A volume of 1 µL of the derivatized samples was injected into the GC-Column DB5-MS (30 m length, 0.250 mm i.d., 0.25 µm film 95 % dimethyl/5 % diphenylpolysiloxane) with a pre-column (10 m J&W integrated with Agilent 122-5532G). The carrier gas was helium, and the flow rate was set at 1 mL·min^{−1}. The injector temperature was set at 250 °C. The split ratio was fixed at 1:12 with 10.19 mL/min helium split flow into an Agilent 5190-2293 Ultra Inert Inlet Liner. The temperature gradient was programmed as follows: the initial oven temperature was at 60 °C (held for 1 min), then it was increased to 325 °C at the rate of 10 °C·min^{−1}, with a cool-down period of 10 min before the next injection. The total analysis time was 37.5 min. The detector transfer line, the filament source, and the quadrupole temperature were respectively set at 280 °C, 230 °C, and 150 °C. The electron impact (EI) source was operated at 70 eV. The mass spectrometer operated in scan mode over a mass range of *m/z* 50-600 at a rate of 5 spectra·s^{−1}. The method was locked at a retention time (RT) of 19.66 min, corresponding with the RT of the internal standard. To adjust the experimental RT to the RI of the library, a calibration FAME mix (Fatty Acid Methyl Ester mix; 0.1 mg·mL^{−1} in CH₂Cl₂) was injected at the beginning of the worklist.

Data treatment. For GC-MS data treatment, a chemical identity was assigned to the compounds by the Unknowns Analysis software (Agilent) by searching in two GC-MS spectral libraries: Fiehn library (Agilent) and NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology, library 2.2 version 2014). Data obtained in the Unknowns Analysis Tool were aligned in Agilent Mass Profiler Professional Version B.13.1 and exported to Agilent MassHunter Quantitative Analysis version B.09.00 to obtain the abundance of the compounds. Finally, the inspection of the correct integration of the peaks was performed and the data matrix was generated [49]. For this technique, 3 experimental samples did not fulfill the quality of the analysis and thus, were excluded from the study.

Quality assurance (QA) and Quality control (QC) analysis

Before, during, and after analysis, QC samples were required. QC was injected at the beginning of the sequence to stabilize the system and throughout the analytical runs at periodic intervals to monitor the stability, performance, and reproducibility of the system. Individual QC samples were therefore prepared independently for each analytical platform by pooling and mixing equal volumes of each sample from the study following the same procedure as applied for the experimental samples [50]. For LC-MS only one QC sample was prepared and injected throughout the experiment, while for GC-MS, 10 individual QCs were prepared independently, and each of them was analyzed twice.

For the quality assurance (QA) of the LC-MS and GC-MS data, raw variables were filtered according to these criteria: 1) features found in blanks (for GC-MS signals from blanks were subtracted while for LC-MS signals higher than 20% in samples were filtered), and 2) absent in more than 50% of QCs. Missing values were replaced using the algorithm *k*-nearest neighbor (KNN) [51]. Then, for GC-MS, data was normalized using Total Useful Signal (TUS) and quality control samples and support vector regression (QC-SVRC) algorithms to correct the instrumental drift. Regarding LC-MS, data normalization was performed using QC-SVRC correction [52]. Finally, for both techniques, data with a coefficient of variation (CV) lower than 20% in the QCs for LC-MS and 30% for GC-MS were kept [53].

Statistical analysis

Multivariate analysis was performed using SIMCA P+14.0 (Umetrics, Umeå, Sweden). Principal Component Analysis (PCA), a non-supervised model, was used to observe data patterns. Likewise, the Partial-Least-Square Discriminant Analysis model (PLS-DA), a supervised model, was used to test differences between the case groups. For LC-MS and GC-MS data, univariate (UV) scaling was used. The robustness of the models was evaluated based on R^2 (explained variance) and Q^2 (capability of prediction) scores [54,55]. Univariate statistics were performed using Mass Profiler Professional v15.1 (Agilent Technologies) applying for the pairwise comparisons t-test unpaired and setting a significance level at 95% (p value < 0.05). For multiple testing corrections, Benjamini-Hochberg FDR was used (Q value). Moreover, for clinical parameters, the frequency of categorical patient variables was calculated and analyzed by Fisher's exact test and Chi-square test. Mean and 95% confidence intervals were calculated for continuous variables and analyzed with ANOVA and t-test. The MetaboAnalyst online tool (v5.0) was used for heatmaps, enrichment analysis, and pathway analysis using significant annotated metabolites.

Results

Clinical description of the subjects

A total of 81 patients were recruited for the study. The clinical parameters of the groups are shown in Table 1. Groups of non-diabetics (ND), diabetics (D), and diabetics with bone fragility (D-Frag) were compared. Among them, statistical differences (p value < 0.05) were found in waist circumference (WC) between ND and both diabetic groups, and in age for ND vs D-Frag. From these data, stacked graphs of sex proportion, CVD, body mass index (BMI), and WC were pictured in Fig. 1-SI. Regarding sex and CVD proportion, the chi-square test showed no influence in the proportion of each condition (p value > 0.05).

General trends of the metabolomic fingerprinting in plasma

Serum samples were characterized using two complementary analytical platforms; LC-MS and GC-MS, resulting in 990 and 209 features for each patient, respectively. A typical chromatogram of each technique is shown in Fig. 2A-SI and Fig. 3A-SI. The quality of the data was assured by the clustering of the QC samples in the PCA plots for each technique (Fig. 4A-SI). Once the quality of the data was checked, PCA and discriminant analysis using PLS-DA of the three main groups together were carried out (Fig. 4B-SI). In the PCA models, a trend of separation of ND against D and D-Frag groups was observed, which was later confirmed with the PLS-DA models. Interestingly, for LC-MS, a bigger separation between the three groups was observed ($R^2=0.61$ compared to $R^2= 0.39$).

Table 1

Clinical parameters of the subjects included in the study.

Group	Non-diabetic (ND)	Diabetic (D)	Diabetic-Bone fragility (D-Frag)	Overall p value	Significant for (p value)
N	28	28	25	–	–
Age (years) (mean \pm SD)	56 (\pm 6)	57 (\pm 7)	60 (\pm 5)	0.033	D-Frag vs ND (0.038)
Sex, n (%male)	11 (36)	13 (50)	13 (54)	0.647	–
BMI (Kg/m ²) (mean \pm SD)	30 (\pm 6)	31 (\pm 5)	32 (\pm 4)	0.333	–
Waist circumference (cm) (mean \pm SD)	98 (\pm 11)	106 (\pm 11)	110 (\pm 11)	< 0.001	D vs ND (0.020) D-Frag vs ND (< 0.001)
CVD, n (%)	–	17 (65)	18 (75)	0.459	–
Glucose (mg/dL) (mean \pm SD)	91 (\pm 11)	182 (\pm 54)	156 (\pm 54)	< 0.001	D vs ND (< 0.001) D-Frag vs ND (< 0.001)
HbA1c (%) (mean \pm SD)	4.85 (\pm 0.4)	8.08 (\pm 1.9)	7.57 (\pm 1.5)	< 0.001	D vs ND (< 0.001) D-Frag vs ND (< 0.001)
Use of Insulin, n (%)	–	17 (65)	16 (67)	0.924	–
Use of Hipoglucemiant, n (%)	–	22 (85)	16 (70)	0.208	–

Legend: BMI, Body Mass Index; CVD, Cardiovascular disease; HbA1c, hemoglobin A1c; SD, standard deviation.

Metabolic profile differences between ND and D patients

To analyze the metabolomic profile related to diabetes, **D vs ND groups** were compared. For this, PCA and PLS-DA models were performed for both techniques (Fig. 1A-B and 1C-D, respectively). The clear separation of both groups was observed in PCA models and was greater in the PLS-DA models. Thus, statistical univariate analysis was performed, leaving 87 and 53 significant features (p value < 0.05 and Q value < 0.05) for LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively. These features were identified resulting in 11 and 33 unique metabolites for each technique (Table 1-SI). These were represented using heatmaps (Fig. 1E-F). From these, we observed an increase of glucose derivates such as fructose, tagatose, and sorbitol, organic acids such as pyruvic acid, α -ketoisocaproate, 2-hydroxybutyrate, and branched-chain amino acids (BCAA) such as valine and isoleucine in D group compared to ND. On the other hand, amino acids such as histidine, tryptophan, lysine, serine, and glycine, and other organic acids such as glyceric acid, caprylic acid, and fumaric acid, were decreased in the D group compared to the ND group. In addition, glycerophosphatidylethanolamines (PE) and LysoPE (LPE) such as PE(36:4) and LPE(20:4), and glycerophosphatidylcholines (PC), and lysoPC (LPC) such as LPC(20:4) were increased in D compared to ND, except PC(34:2)_b which was decreased in D group.

These metabolites were taken to perform enrichment analysis, from which methylhistidine metabolism was the one with the topmost enriched routes (Fig. 1G). These metabolites after pathway analysis showed that aminoacyl-tRNA biosynthesis, BCAA biosynthesis, glyoxylate and dicarboxylate metabolism, glycine, serine, and threonine metabolism, and glycerophospholipid metabolism were significant for the D vs ND comparison (Fig. 1H).

Metabolic differences due to bone fragility in diabetes

Once differences between D and ND patients were assessed, the next step was to analyze the differences in the metabolic profiles of D-Frag patients and D patients (**D-Frag vs D**). Following the workflow of the previous comparison, non-supervised PCA models were carried out showing no separation between groups for GC-MS, but a slight trend of segregation in LC-MS (Fig. 2A-B). Unfortunately, no PLS-DA models were obtained between groups. Nevertheless, univariate analysis was performed to identify as many as possible significant differences between D-Frag and D groups in metabolite concentrations. This analysis resulted in 148 and 8 significant features (p value < 0.05) for LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively. After metabolite annotation, 45 and 7 metabolites were represented in heatmaps for each technique (Fig. 2C-D, Table 2-SI). These results showed a substantial increase of amino acids (lysine, tryptophan), linoleic acid (FA(18:2)), acylcarnitine CAR(18:1), CAR(18:2), and PC(34:2)_b, among others, in D-Frag compared to D group. On the other hand, other lipid classes such as sphingomyelins (SM), PE, other PC, diglycerides (DG), and the LPC(20:4), LPE(20:4) decreased in

Fig. 1. A-B) Non-supervised PCA models and C-D) Supervised PLS-DA models for D vs ND groups for LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively. For multivariate models, key: “ND” (●; blue circle), “D” (●; orange circle), UV scaling was used, and models were autofitted. E-F) Heat maps using the average of the intensities in the samples (represented in columns for each group) and significant (p value < 0.05 and Q value < 0.05) + identified metabolites (in rows) for LC-MS and GC-MS. For lipid annotation [46,47], a level 4 of confidence was followed and was represented by the sum composition of the fatty acids chains and the number of double bonds. In addition, for lipid isomers resolved in retention time (RT), these were indicated with “_a” or “_b”. Red cells represent increased levels of the specific metabolite in that group, whereas blue cells represent decreased levels. G) Enrichment analysis of identified metabolites. H) Significantly altered metabolic pathways for the comparison of D vs ND patients.

(caption on next page)

Fig. 2. A-B) Non-supervised PCA models for D-Frag vs D groups for LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively. For multivariate models, key: “D” (●; orange circle), “D-Frag” (●; red circle), UV scaling was used, and models were autofitted. **C-D)** Heat maps using the average of the intensities in the samples (represented in columns for each group) and significant (p value < 0.05) + identified metabolites (in rows) for LC-MS and GC-MS. For lipid annotation [46,47], a level 4 of confidence was followed and was represented by the sum composition of the fatty acids chains and the number of double bonds. In addition, for lipid isomers resolved in retention time (RT), these were indicated with “_a”, “_b”, or “_c”. Red cells represent increased levels of the specific metabolite in that group, whereas blue cells represent decreased levels. **E)** Enrichment analysis of identified metabolites. **F)** Significantly altered metabolic pathways for the comparison of D-Frag vs D patients.

D-Frag compared to D group. Interestingly, polar metabolites like L-carnitine and methylhistidine were also decreased in D-Frag compared to D. Regarding enrichment analysis, this showed that biotin metabolism and carnitine biosynthesis were the most highly enriched routes (Fig. 2E). These metabolites showed after pathway analysis an alteration of the glycerophospholipid and FA(18:2) metabolism, and lysine degradation (Fig. 2F). Finally, a multivariate ROC curve analysis showed that 27 metabolites out of 54 were needed to obtain an 80.3% predictive accuracy model, with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.871 (Fig. 3-SI). PC, PE, and CAR were the most important metabolites for the multivariate ROC curve as they presented the highest average importance (Fig. 3C-SI).

Influence of sex

Exploring the possibility that sex might be a factor influencing bone fragility, females and males were compared using PLS-DA models (Fig. 4 A-B-IS), proving the difference between them. This made us compare the main groups using single-sex-matched individuals (Fig. 3 C-J-IS). The outcomes proved that male-based models had better quality parameters and differences compared to their female-matched models (Q^2 0.59-0.88 for male-based models vs Q^2 0.26 to 0.55 for female-based models). Even though, separation between D-Frag and D sub-groups was still absent using discriminant analysis models. However, considering that many studies have demonstrated that bone fragility in females might be influenced by several reasons such as hormonal stages and pregnancy [56], we decided to select male samples to study a more homogeneous model. Regarding multivariate analysis, the PCA models using male patients only showed a slight trend of separation between D-Frag and D groups (MD-Frag and MD, respectively) for LC-MS (Fig. 3A-B). However, no PLS-DA models were obtained. Furthermore, univariate analysis between these groups resulted in 82 and 7 features for LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively (p value < 0.05). These features after annotation, led to 35 and 4 metabolites for both techniques (Table 3-SI), which were represented using heatmaps (Fig. 3C-D). Among the changes, data showed a substantial increase of certain carnitines such as CAR(10:0), CAR(6:0), and CAR(8:0), PC (PC(36:5), PC(34:2)_a, and PC(42:0)), and tryptophan in MD-Frag group compared to MD. On the contrary, 2-ketoisocaproic acid, 2-hydroxybutyric acid, and other lipid metabolites such as cholesterol, PE, other specific PC, LPE(16:0), LPC(20:4), and DG decrease in MD-Frag group. These metabolites in the set enrichment analysis showed that mitochondrial beta-oxidation of short-chain fatty acids and phospholipid biosynthesis were the most enriched sets (Fig. 3E), while their pathway analysis showed a serious alteration of the glycerophospholipid metabolism (Fig. 3F). For this comparison, a ROC curve analysis was carried out. We found that all the significant metabolites ($n=39$) lead to a predictive accuracy model of 81%, and an AUC of 0.894. We observed again that CAR, PC, and PE were the metabolites with the highest average impact (Fig. 5-IS).

To observe the number of shared metabolites with the previous comparison, we did a Venn diagram (Fig. 6-SI). We observed that among the shared metabolites ($n=24$), we found PC and PE were the majority ones ($n=20$).

Influence of CVD in diabetes with bone fragility

Considering the existence of underlying common cardiovascular and bone fragility risk factors not fully understood in T2DM population, we

explore the influence of CVD in a fragility model of T2DM. Since our study population has more than 60% of the T2DM patients present CVD and sex was proved as one source of variability, the male patients with CVD and T2DM were selected to observe the influence of CVD on bone fragility. Thus, regarding multivariate analysis, from the non-supervised PCA models a mild separation between MD-Frag and MD both with CVD (i.e. MD-Frag-CVS vs MD-CVD) was observed using the LC-MS platform (Fig. 4A-B). Interestingly, separation between groups was observed using a supervised PLS-DA model for LC-MS (Fig. 4C). After the univariate analysis, 71 and 3 significant features (p value < 0.05) were obtained and resulted in 31 and 2 metabolites from LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively. These metabolites were represented using heatmaps (Fig. 4D-E). Data showed a substantial increase of several PC (including PC (34:2)_a) in MD-Frag-CVD compared to the MD-CVD group. In contrast, a decrease of 2-ketoisocaproic acid, PE, PC, and LPC (LPC (16:1), LPC(18:3), LPC(20:4)), among others, in MD-Frag-CVD compared to MD-CVD group was observed. The significant metabolites were used to perform enrichment and pathway analyses (Fig. 4-FG). The results showed biotin metabolism and glycerophospholipid metabolism as the most enriched set and the only significant pathway, respectively.

Finally, special interest was found in those shared metabolites in at least a couple of comparisons including a D-Frag group (Fig. 7-IS, Table 5-IS, Fig. 2B-SI and Fig. 3BC-SI). We observed that more than 50% of shared metabolites (18 out of 29) were shared between the tree comparisons including the D-Frag conditions. Moreover, the direction of the change was the same, except for one metabolite (Table 5-IS).

Discussion

T2DM is a highly complex disease, associated with a multitude of complications such as bone fragility and/or CVD. However, it remains unclear the reason why only a few of these T2DM patients develop these complications, especially bone fragility. Here, we identified the potential metabolic mechanisms involved in the development of these T2DM complications.

Firstly, we studied metabolites specifically associated with the T2DM condition (D vs ND groups). This comparison showed mainly that hexoses (such as fructose, mannose, and tagatose) and polyalcohols (such as threitol) were increased in the D group compared to ND, as previously described [28]. The increase of hexoses in plasma would be the indicator of a failing internalization of these metabolites in targeted insulin tissues. In the same way, the increase observed in 2-hydroxybutyric acid in the D group, established reliability in our results, as this has been established as a marker of the IR development [57–60]. Regarding amino acids, we observed decreased levels of histidine in the D group, a metabolite typically decreased in obesity [61,62], although the mechanisms regulating the levels of this amino acid in these patients remain unclear. Additionally, we observed decreased glycine levels in the D group which could be associated with increased rates of gluconeogenesis and glutathione consumption as has been previously reported [60]. In addition, previous studies have reported an increase in serine protease inhibitors (serpins) in diabetic patients. Specifically, SerpinB1 levels had been observed a two-fold increase in this population [63]. The rise in levels of this family of inhibitors could lead to reduced serine bioavailability in the body, resulting in decreased glycine levels in these patients. These findings are consistent with the observed decrease in serine and glycine levels in the D group which could serve as a hallmark of IR in these patients [64]. Likewise, a connection between BCAAs and diabetes

Fig. 3. A-B) Non-supervised PCA models for male D-Frag (MD-Frag) vs male D (MD) groups for LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively. For multivariate models, key: “MD” (●; orange circle), “MD-Frag” (●; red circle), UV scaling was used, and models were autofitted. **C-D)** Heat maps using average of the intensities in the samples (represented in columns for each group) and significant (p value < 0.05) + identified metabolites (in rows) for LC-MS and GC-MS. For lipid annotation [46,47], a level 4 of confidence was followed and was represented by the sum composition of the fatty acids chains and the number of double bonds. In addition, for lipid isomers resolved in retention time (RT), these were indicated with “_a”, “_b”, or “_c”. Red cells represent increased levels of the specific metabolite in that group,

whereas blue cells represent decreased levels. E) Enrichment analysis of identified metabolites. F) Significantly altered metabolic pathways for the comparison of MD-Frag vs MD patients.

has been largely reported [28,60,65], so the high levels of BCAAs observed in the D group could also reflect a state of IR and T2DM.

Since the changes observed between D vs ND group were consistent with the published literature, we focused on bone fragility comparison within the T2DM group (D-Frag vs D) to know the specific metabolites involved in disturbed bone metabolism in this pathology. Regarding lipids, compounds such as PC and PE (except one PC) were decreased in D-Frag, suggesting an involvement in bone fragility in T2DM. Most of these classes of lipids are reservoirs of fatty acids, so their decrease, together with the increase of acylcarnitine levels such as CAR(18:2) and CAR(18:1) in the D-Frag vs D group, suggest higher rates of fatty acid β -oxidation in D-Frag to meet the energy demands. Incomplete β -oxidation of fatty acids in mitochondria is common in insulin resistance and T2DM [66]. Previous studies have shown that plasma levels of medium and long-chain CAR are elevated in these disorders and cause mitochondrial dysfunction via complex V (ATP synthase) down-regulation inducing impaired insulin release by pancreatic β -cells [67, 68]. Previous research suggests that CAR may activate inflammatory pathways [69]. Therefore, the accumulation of CAR could affect both the glucose homeostasis and the bone formation.

In addition, a recent study comparing serum samples from patients with low bone mineral density (LBMD) against healthy controls, observed that PC, PE, and LPC significantly dysregulated, all being increased in LBMD compared to controls [70,71]. These findings suggest that these lipid classes might be involved in bone remodeling.

Regarding LPC, it has been observed that LPC induces oxidative stress damage in tissues through the production of ROS [72,73]. Therefore, the LPC decrease observed in D-Frag could suggest an increased catabolism of LPC associated with higher oxidative stress causing an increase in bone loss.

Additionally, the role of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) in bone metabolism has been reviewed by Abshirini *et al.* [74,75], showing that the function of the n-6 PUFA, which include oleic and linoleic acid, treatment produces an enhancement of the thickness of the femur bones in a rat model osteoporosis. So, the increase of linoleic acid in D-Frag compared to the D group, could be related to this mechanism and can act as a compensatory mechanism.

Interestingly, SM were decreased in D-Frag compared to the D group. According to these results, a recent review shows that excessive catabolism of SM is related to bone resorption [76]. SM, a key component of cell membranes, has been involved in bone fragility. Variants in the SGMS2 gene, which encodes the enzyme responsible for SM biosynthesis, have been linked to skeletal dysplasia and osteoporosis [77]. Sphingolipids, including SM, play a crucial role in skeletal tissue formation and maintenance, through regulation by the enzyme SMPD3 [78]. In this context, recent studies demonstrated that sphingosine-1-phosphate receptor 2 agonist, which is involved in SM metabolism, significantly increased the expression of osteoblast differentiation markers and promoted bone formation in a rat model [79]. These findings suggest a potential role for SM in bone fragility. However, further studies are needed to assess the role of the majority of these lipids in bone fragility in T2DM. Furthermore, in the case of tryptophan, its increase in D-Frag of this metabolite and its downstream pathway products have been studied in relation to osteoporotic fractures, mainly in the hip [80,81]. Tryptophan, an essential amino acid, may benefit bone health in individuals with T2DM. Administration of parathyroid hormone (PTH), or certain medications for T2DM, such as dipeptidyl peptidase-IV (DPP-IV) inhibitors and glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) involved in tryptophan metabolism, have shown positive effects on bone health [82–85]. However, their role is still not fully clear.

Moving forward, our male-based model of bone fragility (MD-Frag vs MD) which is less influenced by hormones compared to T2DM females,

represented a more homogenous model. Interestingly, this model shares almost one-third of the same significant changes as for the previous comparison but without the variability of the women due to pregnancies and/or menopause. This comparison showed the same trend for the CAR, PC, PE, and tryptophan as the previous comparison. Of note, 2-hydroxybutyric and 2-ketoisocaproic acids, which are fully described in T2DM, were decreased in the MD-Frag group, however, their role associated with bone fragility has not been elucidated to date.

Finally, in the case of CVD, the comparison between MD-CVD vs MD-Frag-CVD shows with no doubt that the glycerophospholipid metabolism is disturbed. This can be a reflection of the presence of CVD in both groups. However, subsequent analyses are needed in order to unveil the specific side-chain fatty acids of the lipid obtained.

As can be seen from our results, there is an urgent need to identify markers for a better diagnosis and prognosis of T2DM and its complications. This study, while pioneering, has certain limitations. These include a relatively small cohort size, the presence of some unidentified features, and the potential for additional models that were not explored. Despite these aspects, to our knowledge, this is the first pilot study in which key aspects of the bone fragility associated with T2DM have been explored including the sex and the CVD using multiplatform metabolomics. From these, we highlight the analysis of bone fragility in the male population as this would be a clearer model of the pathology. We believe that the findings of this study are of relevance to understand the main metabolic pathways and metabolites that are involved in this complex disease.

Conclusions

T2DM is a multifactorial and complex disease that usually leads to other clinical complications such as bone fragility and CVD. However, it is still unclear the metabolic mechanisms by which these complications are developed. Furthermore, today there is no prognostic biomarker that can be used to diagnose and prevent bone fragility and its association with CVD. This is a study of a unique kind, in which the patients have been studied by important factors such as sex and CVD, trying to elucidate T2DM and their relationship in the development of bone fragility. Among the main metabolite classes involved we observed an increase in the CAR, and a decrease in PC, PE, and SM in D-Frag patients compared to the D group. This study has opened the door to new hypotheses about the disease, which has to be proven in the future to help patients in their treatment and to avoid as far as possible the progression of these T2DM complications.

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Fig. 4. A-B) Non-supervised PCA models for MD-Frag vs MD groups, both with CVD (MD-CVD vs MD-Frag-CVS) for LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively. C) Supervised PLS-DA model for MD-CVD vs MD-Frag-CVS for LC-MS. For multivariate models, key: “MD-CVD” (●; orange circle), “MD-Frag-CVD” (●; red circle), UV scaling was used, and models were autofitted. D-E) Heat maps using the average of the intensities in the samples (represented in columns for each group) and significant (p value < 0.05) + identified metabolites (in rows) for LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively. For lipid annotation [46,47], a level 4 of confidence was followed and was represented by the sum composition of the fatty acids chains and the number of double bonds. In addition, for lipid isomers resolved in retention time (RT), these were indicated with “_a”, “_b”, or “_c”. Red cells represent increased levels of the specific metabolite in that group, whereas blue cells represent decreased levels. F) Enrichment analysis of identified metabolites. G) Significantly altered metabolic pathways for the comparison of MD-Frag-CVD patients vs MD-CVD.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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